

POPMON

**Identification of relevant persistent
organic pollutants and potentially
contaminated regions as the basis for
risk-based food monitoring in Austria**

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POPMON - Identifizierung relevanter persistenter organischer Schadstoffe und potentiell belasteter Regionen als Basis für ein risiko-basiertes Lebensmittel-Monitoring in Österreich

POPMON II - Risikokommunikation und risikobasiertes Monitoring von persistenten organischen Schadstoffen in verschiedenen Umweltmatrices, Futter- und Lebensmitteln an potentiell belasteten Standorten in Österreich

Summary

As part of the project "POPMON - Identification of relevant persistent organic pollutants and potentially contaminated regions as the basis for risk-based food monitoring in Austria", industrial and waste treatment sites, suspected and contaminated sites have been identified as having a potential risk of environmental contamination by persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and subsequently for contamination of food and drinking water. Based on the results of the first project, regions for an emission-based monitoring were identified in rough scenarios in the first phase of POPMON II and two scenarios were selected and further characterised. In the second phase, samples of various relevant matrices were taken at the two locations, examined and assessed for POPs. Planning and implementation took place in coordination with the relevant representatives of the federal provinces. Conspicuous results were already communicated to the relevant state authorities during the project. Finally, further recommendations and measures were discussed with the representatives of the federal provinces in a workshop.

Scenario 1 deals with the investigation of flame retardants and was carried out at the region of Amstetten and Kematen an der Ybbs in Lower Austria. The following POPs were identified as relevant POPs based on the waste treated there and the treatment processes: polychlorinated dioxins, furans and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (PCDD/F and dl-PCB), non-dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (ndl-PCB), chloropesticides, hexabromocyclododecanes (HBCDD), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE) and alternatives to PBDE such as decabromodiphenylethane (DBDPE), dechlorane plus (DP) and hexabromobenzene (HBB). Air (deposition), soil and food of animal origin were examined at this location.

15 soil samples were taken once as well as 5 deposition samples over a period of four months. The selection of the sampling points was made depending on the wind direction and the distance to possible pollutant emitters and included a reference location. The soil analysis showed that increased soil concentrations for PCDD/F and dl-PCBs as well as ndl-PCBs are possible near the industrial area of Amstetten. In general, in most cases there was a decrease in the pollutant concentrations with increasing distance from the possible emission sources. The soil analyses carried out are one-off measurements, so further measurements would be useful and source analyses of this pollutant group (congener patterns, survey for detailed information

on the waste streams used and emission measurements) could provide further insights.

The measured deposition concentrations document a continuous entry of the pollutants into the environment in the vicinity of the industrial areas. Particularly higher values for PCBs in Amstetten are noticeable, which correspond to the measured soil concentrations. The period of the measured deposition concentrations was four months, so no annual mean values could be calculated.

According to the BAT Conclusions for Waste Treatment (Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/1147 of 10 August 2018), the emissions of dioxin-like PCBs from the mechanical treatment of metallic waste in the shredder and the decontamination of equipment containing PCBs and the emissions of PCDD/F from the mechanical treatment of metallic waste in the shredder are to be monitored at least once a year in accordance with EN standards 1948-1, -2, 3-, and -4. Instead of EN 1948-1, sampling can also be carried out in accordance with CEN/TS 1948-5. According to Article 14 (3) of the Industrial Emissions Directive, these BAT conclusions serve as a reference document for the determination of the permit conditions.

BDE 209 dominated among the flame retardants measured, but substitutes such as DBDPE, DP or HBB were also detected in almost all soil and deposition samples. Therefore, further investigations in soil and deposition for other alternative flame retardants and heavy metals would be recommended. For HBCDD, the values measured in the deposition in Amstetten were higher than in Kematen, but an increased value was measured at the forest site of Kematen. Here, too, it would make sense to substantiate the results and limit the contamination by repeated measurements.

15 samples of locally produced food mainly of animal origin, such as milk, cheese, chicken eggs, beef, lamb, pork, bacon, honey and pumpkin seed oil, were taken within a radius of up to 10 km around the industrial areas. The samples comply with the maximum levels for PCDD/F, dl-PCB, ndl-PCB and chloropesticides. The concentration of dl-PCB in a sample of beef from a farm northeast of Amstetten is just below the action level of 1.75 pg/g fat. The highest concentrations of PCDD/F and dl-PCB were found in beef and milk, those of ndl-PCB in lamb. Of the chloropesticides, only hexachlorobenzene was found in the pumpkin seed oil sample in a quantifiable concentration. The tolerable weekly intake for PCDD/F and dl-PCB is only exceeded 1.6 times in children by consuming these foods. The tolerable daily

intake for ndl-PCB is not exceeded by any population group and is only exhausted to a small extent. The minimal risk levels for acute and chronic exposure to hexachlorobenzene are not exhausted by the consumption of pumpkin seed oil. The risk assessment of PCDD/F and dl-PCB shows that a risk for the health of the population cannot be derived, but the intake of PCDD/F and dl-PCB in children should be reduced.

With regard to the detection of flame retardants, PBDE could be found in nine out of fifteen food samples. HBCDD were not detected in the food samples. The highest concentration was measured for BDE 153 in lamb. BDE 126 was most frequently quantified in food. The intake levels of BDE 126, 153 and 209 are very low for all population groups. According to the current state of knowledge, a risk assessment can only be carried out for BDE 153 and 209. No risk for the health of the population can be derived from BDE 153 and 209.

All calculations were based on the assumption that the population exclusively consumes foodstuff from this region examined in the project. Intake through other food categories, such as fish, was not included. These foods can also contribute to the intake of POPs.

Scenario 2 investigated a PFAS contamination in the area of Lebring/Leibnitz in Styria. Here, 22 perfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS), such as perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS), each with their salts and related compounds, were examined. In addition, locally produced food was tested for PCDD/F, dl-PCB, ndl-PCB and chloropesticides. Groundwater, leachate from a disused hazardous site, surface water (fire pond), drinking water, drinking water of animals, blood from farm animals and food of animal origin including fish from local aquaculture were analysed at this location.

In the various water samples, the results show partially increased PFAS values, whereby the random samples selected in the context of these investigations are one-off measurements and were obtained at different sampling times. The substances PFBS, PFOA, PFOS, PFHxS, PFPeS, PFHpA, PFHxA, PFHxS, PFPeA were determined in almost every water sample, whereby PFOS, PFHxS and PFPeS often occurred together at increased levels. PFNA (in drinking water and fire pond), PFHpS (in the disused hazardous site and fire pond), 4:2 FTS (only in two drinking water samples) were rarely detected. 6:2 FTS occurred in higher concentrations only in samples of drinking water of animals and drinking water. 6:2 FTS is often used in electroplating

and filter technology. Since most of the results are single measurements, it would make sense to substantiate the data by repeating measurements. These could be supplemented by measuring the 20 PFAS mentioned in the new EU Drinking Water Directive as well as the total content of organic fluorine compounds in order to obtain a picture of the total contamination with PFAS.

Eight samples of drinking water from different wells in Lebring and Leibnitz and one net sample each from Lebring and Leibnitz were taken and examined for 22 PFAS. Of the 22 PFAS, PFBA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFBS, PFHxS and PFOS were found in quantifiable amounts in all samples. Of these, four samples from Lebring exceeded the parameter value of 0.10 µg/l laid down in the EU Drinking Water Directive. Assuming that the population only consumes drinking water from these wells and the net sample from Lebring, a health risk for the population cannot be ruled out.

In addition, four samples of drinking water of animals were taken on farms and examined for PFAS. Different PFAS could be measured in three samples. One of these samples exceeded the parameter value of 0.10 µg/l for drinking water. PFHxS and PFOS were found most frequently in ten blood samples from eight pigs and two cattle. In four samples of pork and one sample of beef also PFOA was found. In two farms, no or a low PFAS concentration was measured in the drinking water of animals; here the blood and meat were not or only slightly contaminated. If the drinking water of animals was contaminated with PFAS, then PFAS were also present in the blood and meat of animals.

Ten samples of locally produced foods, such as pumpkin seed oil, chicken eggs, beef, pork and carp, were tested for various POPs. The samples comply with the maximum levels for PCDD/F, dl-PCB, ndl-PCB and chloropesticides. The highest concentrations of PCDD/F were found in beef and carp, those of dl-PCB and ndl-PCB in beef and chicken eggs. Of the chloropesticides, only hexachlorobenzene could be measured in pumpkin seed oil. The tolerable weekly intake for PCDD/F and dl-PCB is exhausted once by children. The tolerable daily intake for ndl-PCB is not exceeded by any population group and is only exhausted to a small extent. The minimal risk levels for acute and chronic exposure to hexachlorobenzene are not exhausted by the consumption of pumpkin seed oil. No risk to the health of the population can be derived from PCDD/F, dl-PCB, ndl-PCB and hexachlorobenzene.

The same 10 food samples were also tested for PFAS. Currently no maximum levels have been set for PFAS in food. Elevated concentrations were found in beef, pork

and carp. These samples were also the most heavily contaminated with PCDD/F and PCB. The estimated PFAS intake through locally produced food and drinking water exceeds the tolerable weekly intake 3 to 4.5 times, with drinking water contributing around 60 % to the intake. A risk to the health of the population from PFAS cannot be excluded.

The calculations were based on the assumption that the population only consumes foods and drinking water from this location. Consumption of other food categories, such as milk and dairy products and meat products, was not taken into account. Meat products such as cured meat products and sausages, when made from contaminated meat, can contribute significantly to the intake of POPs.

In a further chapter, the relevant legal matters, responsibilities and information obligations in the food chain area are presented. The hexachlorobenzene contamination case in the Görtschitztal in Carinthia and the groundwater contamination case of Ohlsdorf in Upper Austria are presented as examples of experience in the field of risk communication and crisis management. The PFC case in Rastatt in Baden-Württemberg (Germany) is described with reference to PFAS.

In all of these crises, a crisis management or coordination office was set up, which coordinates the various competent authorities and institutions as well as acts as a contact point or information point for citizens and the media. On the basis of these experiences, it is recommended to take appropriate precautions in order to be able to set up a coordination office more quickly in case of emergency or crisis. This coordination office is also of great advantage in crisis communication in order to provide coordinated, competent and uniform information and to prevent a loss of public trust.

It is also recommended that environmental information relevant to food safety is collected in a structured manner and that the authorities are obliged to exchange this information. Food-related environmental monitoring should be continued or even expanded in order to be able to identify contamination sources at an early stage. This is essential for the clarification, remediation and prevention of further pollution that otherwise remain undetected and can pollute the environment, animals and people with harmful substances.

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